

The Effect of Time of Exposure in Breaking of Seed Dormancy Using H_2SO_4 and Hot Water in *Parkia biglobosa* (Jacq.)Bent and *Phaseolus vulgaris* L.

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Abstract

The seed coat of *Parkia biglobosa* and *Phaseolus vulgaris* are very hard thereby delaying their early germination. The importance of *P. vulgaris* and *P. biglobosa* as food, drug and source of timber leads to their depletion due to high demand for them. It therefore becomes imperative to explore ways of faster emergence and increased germination rate. Hence, this research was undertaken to determine the effect of time of exposure in Hot water and Sulphuric acid in breaking seed dormancy of both seeds. Ninety seeds each of *P. biglobosa* and *P. vulgaris* were soaked in hot water (100°C) and H_2SO_4 (98 %) for 5, 10 and 15 minutes with 0 as control, the experiment was laid out in Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. The experiment was conducted in the Biological garden, Department of Biological Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano. Data was collected on Days to emergence, Germination response, Seedling height Number of leaves and Percentage survival. The data was analyzed using SAS version 9.0. Results of the experiment indicated that both treatments were effective on all the traits studied except for number of leaves in acid at 10 minutes and survival at 15 minutes. Light-red kidney beans emerged faster than locust bean in both treatments, and the acid treatment was more effective in breaking seed dormancy in *Parkia biglobosa* and light red kidney beans than hot water. This research concludes that both treatments are effective and exposure for 5 minutes was most effective.

Keywords: Dormancy, Effect, Hot water, Sulfuric acid, Time.

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1.0 Introduction

Parkia biglobosa also known as African Locust Bean and the light red kidney bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) belong to the family Fabaceae. They are both important sources of food. While the latter is notable for its protein content, the former is also a good source of timber (Olatunji *et al.*, 2013).

Dormancy is an inherent state of growth that is found among all life forms (Footitt *et al.*, 2011).

It helps plants to go through unfavourable weather conditions. However, it is a limitation to the use of seeds to regenerate trees (Ogungbesan *et al.*, 2017) as it may prevent the seeds of these plants from germinating in due time, especially, when the seed coat is too hard. The seed coat of *Parkia* and light-red kidney bean are very hard thereby delaying their early germination. When seed dispersal is hampered for any tropical tree, its extinction risk is exponentially amplified (Caughlin *et al.*, 2015). It has been observed that, the importance of *Parkia*

biglobosa as food, drug and source of timber (Olatunji *et al.*, 2013) leads to its depletion due to high demand for it. As such, it becomes imperative to explore ways of faster emergence and increased germination rate, especially as desire has been expressed to increase the output for food production in order to enhance the sustenance development goal. Different methods have been employed to improve the germinability of different seeds that may have become dormant. Such techniques include the use of sulfuric acid (Oyebamiji *et al.*, (2023) on some forestry trees. Edward *et al.*, (2014) noted that hot water treatment was effective in large seeds of *Albezia lebbeck* producing 67.5% germination. While, Krzysztof *et al.* (2023) reported the use of smoke water to break seed dormancy in Saskatoon berry. Furthermore, scarification of the seeds has also been used to break their dormancy (El Azazi *et al.*, 2013). In this study, the seeds were presoaked in

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sulfuric acid (98 %) and hot water (100°C) with the aim of determining the effect of time of exposure in breaking seed dormancy in *Parkia biglobosa* and Light red kidney beans.1

in each of 5 containers per row including the control in $3 \times 5 = 15$. This was replicated three times and the experiment was laid out in Randomized Complete Block Design.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area and Seed Purchase

The experiment was conducted in the Biological garden, Department of Biological Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano. Seeds of *Parkia biglobosa* and light-red kidney bean were purchased from a market in Badikko area, Kaduna State. They were carefully selected and viability test by floatation conducted (Agbogidi *et al.* 2007; Oyebamiji *et al.* 2023) to ascertain their healthy nature.

2.2 Treatment and Sowing of Seeds

Ninety seeds each of *P. biglobosa* and *P. vulgaris* were soaked in hot water (100°C) according to the modified method of Adeniji *et al.* (2017) and H₂SO₄ (98 %) for 5, 10 and 15 minutes with 0 as control (Amira, 2013). The ones soaked in hot water were allowed to cool while the ones in acid acid were rinsed to remove excess acid. Three seeds were sown

2.3 Data Collection and Analysis

Data was collected on Number of days to emergence (NDE), Germination response, Seedling height (SH), Number of leaves (NL) and Percentage survival (SS) (Odeje and Akor, 2023). The data was analyzed using SAS version 10.0.

4.0 Results

The results of the acid treatment indicated that there was significant difference ($P \leq 0.05$) observed in all traits in all the time of exposure except for the number of leaves (NL) in 10 and 15 minutes respectively (Table 1). Similarly, there was significant effect of the hot water treatments on all the parameters studied except survival percentage at 5 and 10 minutes in hot water (Table 2)

Table 1: Mean square estimate for the treatment of 98% H₂SO₄ in *Parkia biglobosa* and light red kidney bean

TIME	MSV	DF	NDE	GMP	SDH	NL	SVP
5mins	MODEL	4	12.75**	1424.72*	5.17*	1.88**	1224.72*
	ERROR	3	1.00	498.15	1.44	0.00	395.15
10mins	MODEL	5	10.75**	1320.93*	6.56**	1.38 ^{ns}	1250.00*
	ERROR	2	0.17	694.07	0.55	1.79	649.07
15mins	MODEL	4	593.13*	1285.70*	9.75**	0.88 ^{ns}	1285.70*
	ERROR	3	403.46	834.45	0.83	1.13	834.45

Table 2 Mean square estimate of *Parkia biglobosa* and Light red kidney beans treated with hot water

TIME	MSV	DF	NDE	GMP	SDH	NL	SVP
5mins	MODEL	4	5.88**	591.18*	4.46*	1.63*	834.50 ^{ns}
	ERROR	3	5.13	509.91	1.04	0.46	926.80
10mins	MODEL	4	12.75**	1324.72*	3.40*	2.88**	1424.72*
	ERROR	3	1.50	403.25	0.84	0.13	463.15
15mins	MODEL	4	11.88*	350.50 ^{ns}	7.01**	5.87**	312.50 ^{ns}
	ERROR	3	0.17	1265.83	0.52	0.45	1145.75

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The mean performance of the two varieties showed that, LRKB emerged faster than *Parkia biglobosa* in both treatments at all times studied. The fastest day of emergence was 5.75 days when the seeds were soaked in acid for 15 minutes (Tables 3 and 4). On the other hand, *Parkia biglobosa* performed better in

all other traits except number of leaves where there was no significant difference. When the effect of the two treatments were compared, it was observed that, the acid treatment performed slightly better than the hot water treated seeds in terms of days to emergence and the germination response (Tables 3 and 4)

Table 3: Mean performance of the effect of 98% H₂SO₄ at 5, 10 and 15 minutes on growth traits of *Parkia biglobosa* and LRKB

VARIETY	TIME	NDE	GMP	SDH	NL	SVP
P.BIG 1	5mins	9.00 ^a	100.00 ^a	7.60 ^a	6.25 ^a	100.00 ^a
LRKB 2		7.00 ^b	54.15 ^b	5.10 ^b	5.25 ^b	54.15 ^b
P.BIG 1	10mins	8.50 ^a	87.50 ^a	7.95 ^a	6.25 ^a	87.50 ^a
LRKB 2		7.00 ^b	47.48 ^b	5.38 ^b	5.50 ^a	37.48 ^c
P.BIG 1	15mins	7.25 ^b	87.50 ^a	8.98 ^a	6.00 ^a	87.50 ^a
LRKB 2		5.75 ^c	54.15 ^b	6.05 ^b	5.75 ^a	54.15 ^b

Table 4: Mean performance of the effect of hot water at 5, 10 and 15 minutes on growth traits/ of *Parkia biglobosa* and Light-Red Kidney Beans.

VARIETY	TIME	NDE	GMP	SDH	NL	SVP
P.BIG 1	5mins	8.50 ^a	62.50 ^a	7.13 ^a	5.50 ^a	66.67 ^a
LRKB 2		7.75 ^b	37.48 ^b	5.86 ^b	5.25 ^a	49.98 ^b
P.BIG 1	10mins	9.00 ^a	87.50 ^a	7.50 ^a	5.75 ^a	87.50 ^a
LRKB 2		6.50 ^b	54.15 ^b	6.25 ^a	5.50 ^a	54.15 ^b
P.BIG 1	15mins	7.75 ^a	75.00 ^a	8.23 ^a	6.75 ^a	75.00 ^a
LRKB 2		6.25 ^b	62.50 ^b	7.33 ^b	5.00 ^b	62.50 ^b

Means with the same letter within a column are not significantly different

4.1 Discussion

The results of this study showed that the treatments were significantly different at the 95 % level. This is an indication that both treatments were effective in bringing about the breaking of dormancy in both plant species. This confirms the report of Zita *et al.* (2015) who after his research on maize reported that pre-sowing treatments is necessary in seed germination for an improved growth. The effect of acid treatment revealed that, all the seeds that were treated with 98% H₂SO₄ germinated faster than the control. This effect could have resulted from the corrosive nature of the acid thereby removing the hard seed coat of the seeds, and in the process softening them. Similarly, germination percentage was significantly improved after the treatment compared to the control. These results reflect the opinions of El Azazi *et al.* (2017) who improved the

germination of Acacia from 26 to 78 % after using 98 % H₂SO₄ Bhardwaj *et al.* (2016) who reported that, there was maximum germination observed when the seeds of *I. remota* were soaked in Conc.H₂SO₄ for 15minutes and that of Musara *et al.* (2015) who reported that 80 % concentration of H₂SO₄ gave the highest percentage germination of 96 % in *Abelmoschus esculentus*. However they observed that it took between 6 and 12 hours of presoaking to achieve this result. It shows therefore that the present study may be an improvement over that considering that not more than 15 minutes of pre-soaking was used although, it is important to note that this difference may have been due to the difference in concentration of acid used. They used 80% as against the 98 % used in this study. This assertion was further corroborated by Amonum *et al.* (2017)

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although their research materials were pre-soaked for 20 minutes. However, Asmariati *et al.* (2015) reported that, at 98 % concentration no growth was recorded. This may be due to the fact that the research material used by them was probably too soft and destroyed after being soaked for 30 minutes. The results further indicated that the results obtained were dependent on the time of exposure to the treatment (H_2SO_4 and hot water). When the seeds were soaked for 10 minutes, there was greater germination. This was however not significantly different from the treatment at 15 minutes. This suggests that between 5 and 10 minutes would be most ideal in order to populate these two species of plant. This is in line with the finding of Hemen *et al.* (2023). However, they used far shorter time duration (seconds) this probably may not be unconnected with the percentage germination they reported (30%) when they carried out their work on three savanna species. This result is however at variance with the findings of Bhardwaj *et al.* (2018) who reported that a maximum germination of 97.2% was observed when the seeds of *I. remota* was soaked in Conc. H_2SO_4 for 5mins. It is important to note that, seedling height and survival seem to be higher when the seeds were soaked for 15 minutes. Comparing the responsiveness of both research materials, it was observed that light red kidney beans emerged faster than *Parkia biglobosa*. This may be due to the differential hardness of their seed coats as has also been alluded to by Hemen *et al.* (2023), the seed coat of locust bean is harder than that of *P. vulgaris*.

The results of the hot water treatment also indicated that, all treated seeds emerged faster than the control showing the effectiveness of hot water in breaking

References

- Adeniji, I.T., Adeniji, A. M., Wahab, N. T., and Oyedele, M. T. (2017). Evaluation of different pre-treatment techniques for breaking of seed dormancy in *Acacia auriculiformis* (A. Cunn oex Benth). Proceeding of the 39th Annual Conference of the Forestry Association of Nigeria PP39-44
- Agbogidi, O.M., B.O. Bosah and O.F. Eshegbeyi, 2007. Effects of Acid Pre-Treatment on the Germination and Seedling Growth of African Pear (*Dacryodes edulis* Don. G. Lam. H.J.). *International J. Agricultural Research*, 2(11): 952-958.
- Amira, Sh. S. And Mohammed S. A. (2013). Effects of Sulfuric Acid and Hot Water Pre-Treatment on seed germination and Seedling

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seed dormancy. This result is consonance with the findings of Edward *et al.*, (2014) who noted that hot water treatment was effective in large seeds of *Albezia lebbeck* producing 67 .5% germination. However, Ogbu and Awodoyin (2017) opined that it is better to scarify and soak in cold water for 12 hours to bring about maximum germination. They recorded 88 % germination with this technique. The seeds soaked for 15 minutes emerged fastest compared to 5 and 10 minutes. This probably burst faster than the others thereby giving it a head start. However, in comparison with the acid treatment, it was observed that seeds emerged faster and germinated more in the acid treated seeds. This may not be unconnected with the corrosive nature of the acid. However, Oyebamiji *et al.* (2018) reported that seeds soaked in hot water at 100 °C for 5 minutes (HW 100⁰) and sowed in the top soil added with both 120g and 60g of *mycorrhiza* (M120+ and M60+) and sowed in sterilized top soil germinated 13days after sowing. This supports the fact that acid is more effective than the hot water treatment.

5.0 Conclusion

In view of the points raised above, it can be concluded that 98 % H_2SO_4 and hot water are effective in breaking seed dormancy of *Parkia biglobosa* and light-red kidney beans. It can also be concluded that pre-soaking the seeds for 15 minutes in either liquid can bring about faster germination compared with the control. Also, one can infer that acid treatment is more effective in breaking seed dormancy of *Parkia biglobosa* and light red kidney beans,

Growth of *Cassia Fistula* L. *American, Eurasian J. Agric. & Environ. Sci.*, 13 (1):07-15, 2013.

Amonum, J.I., INyam, R. T. and Gbande, S. (2017). Effect of Pre-Treatments on Seed Germination of *Parkia Biglobosa* (Benth). *Journal of Research in Forestry, Wildlife & Environment* Vol. 8(4):

Arowosegbe, S., (2016). Studies on methods of breaking seed dormancy and germination enhancement in *Senna alata* (L.) Roxb. a plant with great medicinal value. *Int. Res. J. Nat. Sci.*, 4: 31-40.

Asmariati purba, Pebri Haloho, and Fauziyah Harahap (2015). Dormancy Breaking Of Red Bean Seeds (*Vigna Angularis*) with Hot

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

- Water, Cold Water and H₂SO₄ Treatment. International Seminar on Trends in Science and Science Education. State University of Medan 12-13 December, 2015
- Bhardwaj, J., Chauhan, R., Nagarajan, S., & Kumar, K. (2016). Pre-sowing treatments for improving seed germination of *Ipomoea remota* Choisy: An endangered medicinal plant. *Journal of Applied Research on Medicinal and Aromatic Plants*, 3(3): 97-101.
- Bhardwaj, J., Chauhan, R., Swarnkar, M. K., & Saini, R. G. (2018). Hormonal regulation of seed dormancy and germination in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Physiology and Molecular Biology of Plants*, 24(5): 855-865.
- Caughlin T.T., Ferguson J.M., Lichstein J.W., Zuidema, P.A., Bunyavejchewin, Sand Levey, D.J. (2015). Loss of animal seed dispersal increases extinction risk in a tropical tree species due to pervasive negative density dependence across life stages. *Proceedings of the British Royal Society*. 282: 2014-2095.
- Edward, M. Alfred, C. and Chikondi, K. (2014). Effects of different pretreatments to the seed on seedling emergence and growth of *Acacia polyacantha*. *Journal of Forestry Research*. 2014: 1-6
- El-Azazi, El-Sayed, Sourour, M. M., Belal, A. H., Khalifa, E. A (2013). Improving *Acacia Tortilis* Seeds Germination by Breaking Dormancy Treatments. *International of Advanced Biological Research* VOL. 3(1) 2013: 103-109
- Footitt, S., Douterelo- Soler, I., Clay, H., Finch-Savage, W. E. (2011). Dormancy cycling in *Arabidopsis* seeds is controlled by seasonally distinct hormone- signaling pathways. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, USA*. 108: 20236-20241.
- Hemen, T. J., Rabi, A. T. and Zayyanu, H. S. (2023) Effect of wet-heat on the seed germination of *Parkia biglobosa* (Jacq Benth) African Locust Bean), *Prosopis Africana* (Guill and Perry)(Nigeria Iron Wood) and *Piliostigma thonningii* (Schumach)(Monkey's bread from the derived savanna zone of Nigeria. *Science Journal of Applied and Natural Sciences (SJANS) Vol 1No. 1* p29-38.
- Krzysztof Gornik, Lidia Sas-Paszt, Lukasz Seliga, Stanislaw Pluta, Edyta Derkowska, Slawomir Gluszek, Beata Sumorok and Walid, E. A. Mosa (2023). The effect of different stratification and scarification treatments on breaking the dormancy of Saskatoon Berry Seeds. *Agronomy* 2023 13, 520 <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy13020520>
- Musara C., J. Chitamba and C. Nuvira (2015). Evaluation of different seed dormancy breaking Techniques on okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.) seed germination. *African Journal of Agricultural Research* 10 (17): 1952-1956
- Odeje, S. C. and Akor D.A. (2023). Effect of Sodium azide on Agro-morphological Traits of Four Varieties of Groundnut (*Arachis hypogea* L.) 1(1):54-60
- Ogbu, J.U., and Awodoyin, R.O. (2017). Pre-sowing treatment of African oil bean (*Pentaclethra macophylla* Benth.) seeds: impact on dormancy break and germination enhancement. *Journal of Tropical Biosciences* 12: 21-26
- Ogungbesan, A. M., Ogunsola, A. R. Lamidi A. and Y. M. Ishiaku (2017). Effect of hot water on the germination rate *Oyebamiji*, N. A., of *Cassia saimeia* L. Seeds. *Agricultural and Food Science Journal of Ghana* 10 (1):780-786
- Oyebamiji, N. A., Ojekunle, O.O., Opanike, O.O. and Yisau J. A. (2023). Effects of pre-sowing techniques on selected seeds of savanna agroforestry tree species. *Journal of the Cameroon Academy of Sciences* 19 (1): 31-41
- Oyebamiji, N. A., Usman, B. and Adelani, D. O. (2018). Pre-germination Treatments on African Locust Beans (*Parkia biglobosa*) Seeds to assess some Growth Indices in Nursery. *Proceedings of the 2nd Commonwealth Forestry Association (CFA)*
- Zita, L., Kovács, G., Szöllösi, R., Szőke, É., & Szőke, C. (2015). Pre-sowing treatments for improving seed germination of maize (*Zea mays* L.) under laboratory conditions. *Scientific Papers. Series A. Agronomy*, 58, 496-500.